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ISMEP-Supmeca: an example of recognition of training on sustainable development and social responsibility through the awarding of the new French “Label DD&RS”

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ABSTRACT

In December 2016, ISMEP-Supmeca, a French public engineering school, obtained a SD&SR (Sustainable Development and Social Responsibility) label for a period of 4 years.

Launched in France in 2015, this "SD&SR label" ("label DD&RS" in French) is the result of the work of many stakeholders: higher education institutions, ministries, associations... Carried out by CIRSES (French higher education SD&SR collective), it is organized around five themes and allows to:

- Promote the best SD&SR initiatives of French higher education and research institutions,
- Upgrade skills within a group of committed institutions.

ISMEP-Supmeca chose to respond to this labeling approach. In this paper, we will first focus on the SD&SR label. Then, we will present the approach of ISMEP-

Supmeca and detail the strategic variables of the education axis of the label through the sustainable development education policy developed at ISMEP-Supméca:

- Train and prepare engineering students for tomorrow's issues, problems and jobs, emphasizing the initiatives and opportunities presented by SD&SR,
- Continue to gradually integrate SD&SR as tied approach, knowledge and skills in all modules, projects and courses offered in the curriculum.

We will conclude with a focus on one specific action undertaken at ISMEP-Supmeca, the “SD&SR days”.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Ethics in Engineering Education, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Sustainable development and social responsibility, Engineering Education, Labeling

INTRODUCTION

ISMEP-Supmeca is a human-sized French public engineering school, located in a rapid-changing part in the north of the Great Paris area and engaged in sustainable development and social responsibility policies for many years.

In 2016, the institution decided to engage into the recognition of this engagement and the result was obtained quickly: ISMEP-Supmeca was awarded a SD&SR (Sustainable Development and Social Responsibility) label for a period of 4 years.

In the first part, we will present this "SD&SR label" (“label DD&RS” in French), launched in 2015 and the result of the work of many stakeholders: higher education institutions, ministries, associations...

Then, in the second part, we will present ISMEP-Supmeca and especially focus on the approach of the institution towards SD&SR in general and the education axis in particular, with references to the specific SD&SR education policy and to the so-called “SD&SR days”.

1 THE FRENCH SD&SR LABELING SYSTEM

1.1 Some words and facts about the French SD&SR label and its operator

France has a higher education system involving two main kinds of institutions providing education: universities and Grandes Ecoles (engineering schools and business schools). It has also bodies playing a great role like the Conference of Grandes Ecoles and the Conference of University Presidents. Finally, it has a strong accreditation history, with, for example, the CTI (Commission des Titres d’Ingénieur), engineering accreditation institution, which introduced high-level standards and is now paying a lot of attention to topics like SD&SR.

Created and launched in France in 2015, the "SD&SR label" (label DD&RS in French) labeling system is the result of the collective work of a dozen universities and so-called “Grandes Ecoles”, the Conference of Grandes Ecoles, the Conference of University Presidents, the Ministry in charge of Sustainable Development, the Ministry in charge of Higher Education and the French Network of Students for Sustainable Development.

It meets the implicit demand of a growing number of institutions developing initiatives and it is fully in line with the article #55 of the first so-called “Grenelle environnement” (open multi-party debate in France that brings together representatives of national and local government and organizations).

The label, based on a self-assessment tool “SD&SR framework”, is carried out by CIRSES (French acronym for Collective for the Integration of Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development in Higher Education), the latter being an association with three main objectives:

- To support the persons in charge of the SD&SR mission in the higher education institutions,
- To contribute to the influence of the SD&SR initiatives of the higher education institutions,
- To be the reference in terms of SD&SR practices in the French higher education and research area.

Concretely, the SD&SR label is accompanying the objectives presented above. Its main aims are to:

- Promote nationally and internationally the best SD&SR initiatives of the French higher education and research institutions,
- Upgrade skills in the framework of a group of committed institutions.

Labelling sessions took place, under a process and with first results presented hereafter.

1.2 How it works and first results

Two labelling sessions have already taken place since the label began to work: the 2015-2016 winter session (from October 2015 to May 2016) and the 2016 summer session (from March 2016 to December 2016). Each session starts with the application period, followed by the assessment by auditors, then by a direct audit and is closed by a meeting of the labelling committee, officially awarding or not the label.

The whole evaluation process is based on a SD&SR assessment grid organised around 5 main axes:

- 1. Strategy and governance,
- 2. Education,
- 3. Research,
- 4. Environmental management,
- 5. Social policy and territorial rooting.

These axes and more generally the grid are referring to the axes defined in the so-called Green plan constructed by the stakeholders of the higher education and research area and already tested with success by more than 100 institutions since 2012.

Each institution aiming to apply has to provide a self-assessment of its SD&SR policy by filling in the assessment grid, each axis containing sub-topics and then each sub-topic containing sub-items. This has to be completed by supporting documents.

The first assessment, done on these documents, is completed by an assessment meeting with representatives of the applicant institution. Both parts of the assessment process result in awarding the label or not.

A total of fourteen institutions was awarded during the two first labelling sessions: ten engineering schools, two business schools and two universities. More institutions have already applied, will apply and will be awarded the label in the coming months.

ISMEP-Supmeca is one of these first fourteen institutions, which responded to the second application wave at a moment corresponding to its wish to see its actions recognised. Hereafter we will focus on the institution SD&SR actions and policy.

2 ISMEP-SUPMECA: AN INSTITUTION WITH A RECOGNIZED SD&SR POLICY

2.1 From the first actions to the SD&SR label award

ISMEP-Supmeca is French public engineering school, giving to its students a three-year engineering education (1/3 of internships; 1/3 of projects and experimentation; 1/3 of courses and supervised practical work), making them specialists in modelling, conception and production systems, who will mainly join large industrial companies. The school hosts globally around 600 students on these three levels (for example, in 2016-2017: 490 students in a classic engineer curricula, 140 students in an apprenticeship engineer curricula and 16 students in a specialized or advanced master on lean management), making in a human-sized school. It also has a global staff of around 200 people (permanent and non-permanent).

ISMEP-Supmeca is located in Saint-Ouen, in Seine-Saint-Denis department, i.e. in a rapid-changing part of the north of the Great Paris area. Being one of the only two public engineering schools of this department, ISMEP-Supmeca also faces challenges due to its location in a dense residential and post-industrial urban area.

Taking all these aspects into account, ISMEP-Supmeca engaged step-by-step into a real SD&SR approach in 2010, the SD&SR label obtained being the concretization of both the engagement and the strategy.

The first actions in favor of the development of a SD&SR were taken in 2010 and were from the beginning placed in the larger framework of a real strategy. Indeed, a SD&SR officer started working in June 2010 and this was followed by the first steering committee until the design and writing of the first SD&SR charger of the institution in November 2010.

From that date and under the supervision of different persons in charge of the management of the SD&SR policy (in addition to their initial tasks at ISMEP-Supmeca), this policy grew, with many particular actions. We can quote among others the following ones:

- Development of an apiary,
- Writing of a monthly SD&SR info-flash,
- Provision of electrical bikes to ISMEP-Supmeca staff members,
- Student association doing remedial courses for children from Saint-Ouen and neighbouring municipalities,
- Formalisation and co-building of the professional training for the staff,
- Diagnostic of psycho-social risks.

All these actions are integrated into five axes defined previously in this article and also integrated into the SD&SR strategy of the institution. Revised in 2016, this strategy defines two main SD&SR wishes for ISMEP-Supmeca:

- Acting with students, who will be the main SD&SR vectors in the context of their future professional life,

- Training all the students so that they can be ready and able to make an energy balance, a carbon assessment and a lifecycle analysis.

The secondary wishes of the school defined in the SD&SR strategy are the following:

- Promote SD&SR through concrete actions,
- Use the family size of the school in order to conduct projects involving staff, students and graduates,
- Be a pioneer in its territory and be more open towards its territory.

This global SD&SR strategy is completed by a specific SD&SR educational strategy, linked to the “Education” axis of the Green plan or SD&SR label assessment grid.

Beyond the actions and the formalisation into the strategy, there is the third very important point: the involvement of the stakeholders. There is a core group of people, both staff and students, who make SD&SR a reality at ISMEP-Supmeca. Several student associations (Soutien Scolaire Supmeca, involved in remedial courses, Ecostudent or New Defi) and a small group of key staff members are very involved in these issues, being pro-active and available.

After six years of actions, it was decided to try to gain a recognition for the work done and to apply for the SD&SR label in order to receive this recognition.

As presented in figure 1 hereafter, the institution was assessed 3 out of 5 in four of five axes (Strategy and governance, Education, Environmental management, Social policy and territorial rooting), and received 2 out of 5 in the Research axis, which is, according to CIRSES, the most difficult to get a good mark.

Fig. 1. Performance summary of ISMEP-Supmeca at the SD&SR (“DD&RS” in French) labelling session

The awarding of the label for a period of four years (with mid-period self-assessment to provide) and the 3 out of 5 marks obtained on four axes reflect the work done and could have been even better with a better formalisation of the actions, especially in the Education axis, where more and more is being done.

2.2 Education first: responsible engineers for the twenty-first century

The specific SD&SR educational strategy developed at ISMEP-Supmeca is linked to the “Education” axis of the Green plan or SD&SR label assessment grid and makes the integration of SD&SR possible at different levels and different moments of the curricula, in order to make the future engineers responsible engineers able to work and behave like ducks in the water in the twenty-first century. The main elements resulting from this strategy and present in the curricula are:

- Integration of SD&SR issues into the internship reports (4-week operator internship in the first year, 18-week assistant-engineer internship in the second year, 24-week engineer internship in the third year),
- Integration of SD&SR issues in the framework of problem- and project-based pedagogy: PRIM module (Mechanical Engineering project / 26 half-days per student in the first year), PLACIS project (5-month project for incoming students in the second year), Design office project (25 half-days per student in the second year), Synthesis project (48 half-days per student in the third year), PLACIS project (48 additional half-days to the synthesis project in the third year),
- Core course on Ecological footprint of the systems / 24-hour course for second-year students (20 hours for apprenticeship students) corresponding to 2 ECTS,
- Elective course on Ecodesign of Systems / 32-hour course in the second year corresponding to 2 ECTS,
- SD&SR days, developed in the next part of this paper.

This list can be divided into four parts: internships, projects, classical courses and special days. The projects are very interested here as they already share common values with SD&SR, especially the PRIM module and the PLACIS projects.

PRIM module is a full multidisciplinary problem-based module using topics like wind turbine conception in order to teach a bench of mechanical courses and associated skills.

PLACIS projects are multidisciplinary and systems-oriented projects, most of them being multi-semester, international, industrial and addressing direct SD&SR issues, like electrical and hybrid vehicles, biomimicry, eco-planes of the future... One of the important added-value of these projects is that they teach students how to work collaboratively, at-a-distance, on real long-term projects.

Also, the two classical courses presented above lead to specific SD&SR skills and competencies, but they are not the only ones. Courses linked to systems engineering and systems analysis or linked to materials also lead to SD&SR skills. For this reason, responding to a demand from both the CTI and the SD&SR label auditors, SD&SR issues are being clarified or introduced in a growing number of courses and under new formats, which tend to be successful, as proven by the SD&SR days presented in-depth at a recent congress in France [1] and briefly presented hereafter.

2.3 The SD&SR days: an example of training initiative

There are two SD&SR days: a half SD&SR day for first-year students and a SD&SR day for third-year students. Set up for several years, the DD & RS days were initially in a classic format of conferences by experts in topics like wind energy or cooperative

companies. These conferences met limited success and students asked for an evolution towards a less passive format, both agreed and pushed by the staff.

These days have therefore evolved into a participatory format allowing to better capture their students' attention, as well as stimulating imagination and exchanges. This evolution was carried out in a progressive way: a transition to a participative format for the half-day for first-year students in 2015-2016, and then, regarding the success, a transition to the same participative format for both days in 2016-2017.

Concretely, the half-day for first-year students takes place in the following way: the students, divided into two rooms, work in groups by brainstorming method and then perform a pooling and restitution by room before one or more professional(s), who comment on the renditions and then present their experiences. For example, in 2015-2016 and 2016-2017, the objectives of the students were to: 1. define the SD&SR and imagine themes, missions, objectives, skills, interlocutors, problems of a SD&SR manager in a SME or a large group; 2. Imagine interactions and constraints related to the SD&SR of an engineer when he is in office.

The SD&SR day for students of the third year has also been participatory since 2016-2017: the morning is devoted to brainstorming and pooling; the afternoon to presentations and interventions. This day proposed for its first edition a prospective reflection around seven themes (passenger and freight transport, management of nuisances, well-being at work, circular economy ...), each of which treated by two groups, which later pooled and presented their results in the form of mental maps.

Fig. 2. Examples of mental maps produced by the students (in order to see the diversity of paths followed)

Not only the SD&SR topics were an added value for the students, but also the tools: both mental map and brainstorming were new for most of them. Even if not fully appropriately used by everyone, these tools brought positive results about their use by the persons attending these days, including professional ones.

One very positive point is that professionals highly rated their involvement in these days, but also students highly valued the participation of the professionals, who had the opportunity to present concrete experiences and engage the debate on some issues. High-rank persons from Kering, Alstom and SNCF Réseau already participated, the two latter ones based in Seine-Saint-Denis department and enforcing the local rooting of ISMEP-Supmeca.

The feedback to these events is very positive. Satisfaction surveys (questions on the principle of the day, the program, the participative format, the interventions, and the presentations for third year students) conducted after each event indicate for example that first-year students endorse very much the participative format and third-

year students also attach great importance to the presence of an enthusiastic external professional commentator. If we convert the evaluations to a score of 20, for the academic year 2016-2017, the half-day for first-year students was rated 14.7/20 and the day for third-year students was rated 13.9/20.

There are three categories of comments enclosed to the answers to the surveys:

- The positive ones, being the large majority, for example:
 - "extremely interesting, to be renewed absolutely for future promotions, this day reinforced me in the idea of wanting to work in SD&SR",
 - "format more interesting than the usual conferences",
 - "well to do a brainstorming",
 - "Interaction with professional stakeholders: ++".
- The ones asking for changes or expressing proposals, like the following ones:
 - "to be done in September or October",
 - "more actions are needed: garbage collection in parks".
- The sceptical or negative ones, like the following ones:
 - "concept rehashed for nearly 20 years",
 - "we are sensitized on themes on which we have no influence".

We took very much into account the two last categories of comments. For example, these events will take place earlier in the calendar from 2017-2018. Also, we think that resignation or criticism are linked to the fact that for some students, SD&SR is reduced to its environmental aspect. In order to counter that, we will focus more on economic and societal issues in the monthly SD&SR info-flashes. We will also try to make sure that as many students as possible are aware of the possibility, as engineers, of influencing a certain number of choices and conducting a systemic reflection integrating all the SD&SR parameters, despite various constraints which they will confront.

3 GOING FURTHER

Empowering the students and making them aware of the possibilities and limits they will have in their jobs and lives join the main SD&SR wishes of ISMEP-Supmeca. Linking SD&SR with project-based learning is already done and linking it with entrepreneurship is on the to-do list of the institution, the latter aiming to go further in terms of actions and formalization.

Moreover, following both the continuous improvement approach promoted by CIRSES and the need for transdisciplinary approaches, more and more courses will be featured with references to SD&SR issues will lead to the gain of SD&SR-linked skills. The ongoing improvement and lifting of the syllabus of the institution will fasten this process, which will also need to be discussed with all the teachers involved, in order to enjoy the best understanding of the place of SD&SR issues in the different courses and taking into account the main learning outcomes and pedagogy approaches of these courses.

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